

Product Vision RMS-P

Date

November 2024

Created by

Emma Schreurs, Frans Oort, Tako Horsley

Preface

The current 'Research Management Services' (RMS) platform aims to assist researchers, support staff and management with a wide range of administrative tasks throughout the research life cycle. The development of the RMS has proved challenging on the used software platform. Before making any consequential changes, we need to reassess whether our original plans for the RMS are still valid or need to be updated and extended. Therefore, this document presents a new product vision for RMS. The envisioned product has been named the 'Research Management Services Portal' (RMS-P).

In order to create this vision, the authors first drafted a version on the basis of the original RMS plans (2019) and the IT-Infrastructure report (2024). This draft was then reviewed and discussed with many people with various roles within the faculties and research institutes of the University (see Appendix A). The report was finalised on the basis of the results of this review. Chapter 1 describes the reasons for establishing the RMS-P, Chapter 2 lists all the possible functions of the RMS-P, and Chapter 3 concludes with some additional remarks including key concerns for the next steps.

Contents

1	The Research Management Services Portal.....	4
1.1	RMS-P for researchers.....	4
1.2	RMS-P for support staff.....	4
1.3	RMS-P for directors and management staff.....	5
2	Overview of functionalities.....	5
	Figure 1: Overview of modules and (connected) features within the RMS-P	6
	Figure 2. First example of the main page of the RMS-P, for researchers	7
	Figure 3. First example of the main page of the RMS-P, for support staff	8
	Overview RMS-P Components and Modules.....	9
3	Concluding remarks	20
	Appendix A: Reviewers and interviewees	22

1 The Research Management Services Portal

Research at the University of Amsterdam (UvA) must comply with relevant laws and regulations (such as the GDPR), institutional policies (such as data management, ethics, and security), Open Science principles (such as FAIR data and software), and the Dutch Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (such as transparency and traceability). The UvA has a duty of care to establish and maintain an infrastructure that supports researchers in meeting these requirements while also facilitating compliance without adding unnecessary workload.

To meet these needs, we want to develop a comprehensive Research Management Services Portal (RMS-P), which will:

1. Provide comprehensive support to researchers throughout the entire research lifecycle;
2. Ensure compliance with applicable laws, regulations, and institutional policies, such as privacy and security policies, knowledge safety, the Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, Open Science principles, RDM guidelines, etc.;
3. Balance centralisation and decentralisation of (IT) support infrastructures;
4. Be user-friendly for both researchers and support staff;
5. Integrate seamlessly with existing UvA services, such as those offered by ICT Services (ICTS), the Library, Project Control, Innovation Exchange Amsterdam (IXA), and the faculties and research institutes;
6. Enhance compatibility with external services providing storage, (high performance) computing, data repositories, publication platforms, and grant request (funding) portals.

This document provides a product vision for the Research Management Services Portal (RMS-P), building upon the original plans for the RMS. The RMS-P should be user-friendly, with a primary focus on meeting the needs of its main users: **researchers** and **support staff**. It should offer simple, intuitive workflows with as much automation as possible.

1.1 RMS-P for researchers

In the RMS-P, researchers can find, register, and manage everything they need to support their research activities throughout *the entire* research cycle, from study preparation to the archiving and publishing of research results, and everything in between.

Through the RMS-P, researchers can access:

- UvA-generic, and faculty- or institute-specific research-information resources.
- Central services as provided by ICTS, the Library, IXA, etc.
- Decentral services as provided by faculties and research institutes.
- Administrative and legal procedures necessary for their research discipline, ensuring compliance with applicable laws, regulations, and institutional policies or guidelines, including support for ethics reviews, data management plans, contract drafting, etc.

1.2 RMS-P for support staff

In the RMS-P, support staff will have access to all essential tools and workflows needed to assist researchers effectively throughout the entire research lifecycle. This support can be provided from within individual organisational units, such as within faculties and research institutes (e.g., by data

stewards, ethics committee members, privacy officers), or from central services such as Legal Affairs, IXA, the Library, or ICTS.

Through the RMS-P, support staff can access and manage:

- UvA-wide, as well as faculty- and institute-specific research resources;
- Support workflows for data management plans, ethics reviews, grant proposals, collaboration agreements or contracts, data processing agreements, data transfer agreements, etc.;
- Overviews of open support requests, enabling efficient tracking of progress and direct communication with support when needed;
- Up-to-date insights into ongoing and completed research projects.

1.3 RMS-P for directors and management staff

Lastly, the RMS-P will generate usage and progress reports for research directors and administrative staff, providing a comprehensive overview of research activities and system utilisation.

2 Overview of functionalities

We think of the RMS-P as a web page that displays several ‘tiles’ related to the different modules. By clicking on the tiles, you can unlock their content and (support) features. The configuration of displayed modules and their specific features will vary based on user roles (e.g., institute director, principal investigator, researcher, support staff), as well as the research discipline. Some modules have their own independent functionality and workflows, but many modules are linked to existing information resources and connected to other research infrastructure components through a system interface, for instance an API.

Thanks to its modular structure, research institutes can decide which modules to use, and which modules or features are required or optional. Modules can be adapted to meet discipline-specific needs or institute-specific policies if this enhances operational effectiveness. A balance should be struck between implementing custom solutions when necessary and maintaining administrative and cost efficiency whenever possible. During implementation, it is important to engage with all stakeholders, to see to what extent procedures can be standardised and to what extent central services can be used. In fact, the implementation of the RMS-P can be instrumental in promoting standardisation of procedures and the use of central services. To make things as easy as possible for users (i.e., researchers and support staff), the RMS-P should be intuitive, and workflows should be structured and automated as much as possible.

Figure 1 below provides an overview of the RMS-P components with (connected) features/ functions to support the researchers and research support staff in their research activities. All modules and their (support) features are listed with short descriptions after the figure. It should be noted that this overview is not a representation of the user interface to be created for the RMS-P. A first tentative sketch of the main page for two roles, the researcher and the research support professional, when they log in to the RMS-P is provided in Figures 2 and 3 below. This main page and all subsequent pages/views related to the different modules incorporating or integrating different functions and workflows will be detailed and optimised over time with the help of UX design including several review sessions.

Figure 1: Overview of modules and (connected) features within the RMS-P.

Figure 2. First example of the main page of the RMS-P for researchers.

Figure 3. First example of the main page of the RMS-P for research support staff.

Overview RMS-P Components and Modules

- A. Information and Support 11**
 - A1. Search & Consult Research (Support) Information 11**
 - a. Information Provision..... 11
 - A2. Request Support & Track and Trace Requests in Time..... 11**
 - a. General Research Support 11
 - b. Consultancy for Methods, Statistics, and Data Science 11
 - c. On- and Off-boarding 12
- B. Research Management 12**
 - B1. Check & Submit Grant Applications 12**
 - a. Project Control 12
 - B2. Register & Organise / Manage & Complete Research Projects..... 12**
 - a. Project Registration..... 12
 - b. Pre-registration 12
 - c. Software Management Plan..... 13
 - d. Lab/ Research Data Journals 13
 - e. GDPR Processing Register 13
 - f. Management Reports 13
 - B3. Register & Assess (risk) Issues / Update & Add Assessments 14**
 - a. Ethics Review/ Informed Consent 14
 - b. Advisory Committee - Sensitive Collaborations 14
 - c. Data Management Plan..... 14
 - d. Information Security & Privacy Risk Analysis 14
 - e. Data Protection Impact Assessment 15
 - B4. Create & Conclude Agreements / Update & Add Agreements 15**
 - a. Privacy Agreement 15
 - b. IXA - Collaboration Agreements, NDAs, etc. 15
 - c. Data Transfer Agreements 16
 - B5. Organise Studies-Experiments & Request Research (Lab) Facilities 16**
 - a. Documenting and Planning Studies / Requesting Facilities 16
- C. IT and (Meta) Data Management 16**

C1. Advice on IT for Project / Request, Manage, & Access IT Facilities	16
a. Decision Guide for IT Facilities for Data Storage, Management and Analysis.....	16
b. User Group and Access Management for IT Facilities.....	16
C3. Store, Update, Check, & Publish Metadata	17
a. Metadata Management	17
C4. Check, Archive & Publish Data / Register & Publish Research Output	17
a. Data Archiving	17
b. Data Publication	17
C5. Request Archived Data for Reuse	18
a. Data Reuse	18
D. Workflow Support	18
D1. Workflows for Routing, Guidance, & Communication	18
a. Modular.....	18
b. Referral and Guidance.....	18

A. Information and Support

A1. Search & Consult Research (Support) Information

a. Information Provision

The RMS-P can include or refer to appropriate information resources or knowledge bases. It can include a comprehensive list with generic and more discipline-specific research subjects for both scientific and support staff including available software licenses and IT facilities for storage and computing. Moreover, it can include an overview of available scientific training and development opportunities, e.g., provided by the Digital Competence Centre (DCC). Although there are several resources (e.g., A-Z lists, rsp.uva.nl) centrally and at the faculty level, the goal is to combine all information for research into a single searchable list accessible within the RMS-P.

Why is it necessary? Research related information is currently fragmented across many different resources and is often outdated. We need to ensure that research information services are up to date, and easy findable and fully searchable through one centralised portal.

Parties involved: Research institutes, researchers, supporters, local/ central RMS-P content editors and administrators, Library and ICTS.

A2. Request Support & Track and Trace Requests in Time

a. General Research Support

The RMS-P can enable researchers to request research related support. This involves a broad range of support provided at the faculty (for proposal/ grant, RDM/ IT, security/ privacy, etc. related issues) and centrally provided by the Library, ICTS, the legal department, Chief Information Security (CISO) and Data Protection Officers (DPO), Department of Records and Information Services (DIV), etc.

Why is it necessary? Currently various ways exist to request research-related support, and it can take a long time to figure out where you can get the needed support. We need a more immediate and clear-cut way for support requests, accessible through one portal (i.e., a so-called 'one-stop-shop'). Moreover, the ability to track and trace requests (i.e., follow their progress in time) would really be helpful.

Parties involved: Researchers, data stewards, local/ central IT & RDM support, CISO, DPO, legal department, DIV, and local/ central RMS-P administrators.

b. Consultancy for Methods, Statistics, and Data Science

Consultancy is available to all researchers who need support in research methodology data analyses/ science, and/or statistical analyses. For instance, data science is supported by the Data Science Centre (DSC), and research methodology and statistics is supported by the Social and Behavioural DSC (SoBe DSC). Both can be facilitated through the RMS-P.

Why is it necessary? Currently, there is insufficient awareness about the availability of consultancy for researchers on methodology, data analysis/science, and statistics. The RMS-P can provide appropriate information about consultancy and can support related workflows involving consultants.

Parties involved: Consultants, researchers, and local/ central RMS-P content editors and administrators.

c. On- and Off-boarding

The RMS-P can play a role during the on- and off-boarding process. When on-boarding, the RMS-P can refer to the appropriate sources and entail procedures for new scientific and support staff to get acquainted with the organisation and the way of working. When off-boarding, the RMS-P can refer to the appropriate sources and entail procedures to facilitate the transition of researchers to another institute, such as closing temporary workspace storage and establishing a data transfer agreement allowing the continuation of research data use.

Why is it necessary? The RMS-P can become a portal in which researchers can find all information and support essential for their work, including on- and off-boarding processes.

Parties involved: Researchers, research directors, support staff, and local/ central RMS-P content editors and administrators.

B. Research Management

B1. Check & Submit Grant Applications

a. Project Control

Project controllers guide and advise researchers on second-flow (NWO grants) and third-flow (contract research) funded projects. In addition to providing advice and information, project controllers assist with project budgets, grant requirements, administration of project budgets, contract negotiation for EU grants, provision of periodic reports (to grant providers), preparation of audit files, and the recruitment of (support) staff on research projects. The RMS-P could facilitate all activities of project controllers by providing workflow support and relevant research project information.

Why is it necessary? Project control offices provide necessary research project management and support to researchers. Related functionalities and workflows can be facilitated through the RMS-P.

Parties involved: Project controllers, research directors, researchers, and local/ central RMS-P content editors and administrators.

B2. Register & Organise / Manage & Complete Research Projects

a. Project Registration

Project registration in the RMS-P serves as a place holder for all procedural registrations and assessments concerning, among others, the Data Management Plan (DMP) and the ethics review. The project form asks for common information about the project, such as the title, principal investigator's name, and project duration. It provides a general overview of the project and only has to be provided once and can be re-used in other registrations when needed. The RMS-P can offer research institutes, researchers, and support staff a comprehensive overview of all ongoing research projects.

Why is it necessary? Researchers and support staff involved in the project need to be able to keep track of the project status and progress (including outstanding requests, checks, etc.).

Parties involved: Researchers, and local/ central RMS-P content editors and administrators.

b. Pre-registration

The RMS-P can provide an option to 'time stamp' and archive research information such as research protocols and data analysis plans, etc.). Pre-registration does not require reviews by support staff.

Why is it necessary? Pre-registering is increasingly recognised as a crucial step in promoting research integrity and transparency. The RMS-P promotes awareness among researchers about the significance of pre-registration and facilitates the process to pre-register.

Parties involved: Researchers and local/ central RMS-P content editors and administrators

c. Software Management Plan

The RMS-P can make Software Management Plans (SMPs) available to all researchers who develop software. These plans contribute to software accessibility, reusability, and when used for data analysis, result in reproducibility. This also helps to promote collaboration on software development and use of open-source software for research.

Why is it necessary? SMPs are prerequisites to implement best practices for software development and use.

Parties involved: Researchers, data stewards, software/ data engineers, local/ central RMS-P content editors and administrators.

d. Lab/ Research Data Journals

Lab/ Research Data Journals or integration with existing ones (templates or applications) can be provided in the RMS-P. A Lab/ Data Journal serves as a protocol description (i.e., predefined set of rules or procedures) and a logbook (to record states, events, or conditions) during the research project, mostly related to data collection and processing.

Why is it necessary? Integrating Lab/ Data Journals in the RMS-P may be helpful for researchers who use them. Moreover, they may contribute to the transparency and reusability of research data. The RMS-P can either provide a selection tool for Lab/ Data Journals or can provide procedures/ templates itself.

Parties involved: Researchers and local/ central RMS-P content editors and administrators.

e. GDPR Processing Register

The RMS-P can maintain a processing register containing all information on personal data processed for each research project. This register needs to be based on previously registered project information in the RMS-P.

Why is it necessary? Keeping an GDPR processing register is a legal obligation for the UvA.

Parties involved: DPO, privacy officers, local/ central administrators RMS-P content editors and administrators.

f. Management Reports

RMS-P can provide the functionality to generate various management reports with all kinds of research project information, also including summary statistics and information on the use of the RMS-P. Research directors and other entitled staff can obtain insight into the research projects directly from the RMS-P.

Why is it necessary? Management reports provide data and insights that plays a role in decision-making, communication, and compliance within the organisation.

Parties involved: Research directors, information managers, privacy officers, DPO, CISO, local/ central RMS-P content editors and administrators.

B3. Register & Assess (risk) Issues / Update & Add Assessments

a. Ethics Review/ Informed Consent

The Ethics Review (ER) and Informed Consent can be facilitated in the RMS-P. The ER includes questions about participant recruitment, inclusion, exclusion criteria, etc. The legal basis for processing personal data (mostly Informed Consent), can be part of the ER, or can be provided separately.

Why is it necessary? Ethics reviews are necessary for ethics committees to check compliance with ethical guidelines for each research project that requires an ethics review. The legal basis for processing personal data can be integrated into this process or closely linked to it, as both the ethics committee and data stewards need to review the legal basis.

Parties involved: Researchers, ethics committees, data stewards, and local/ central RMS-P content editors and administrators.

b. Advisory Committee - Sensitive Collaborations

Access to the 'Advisory Committee on Sensitive Collaborations' can be facilitated in the RMS-P. Collaborations with third parties may in some cases lead to unethical use of research results by parties who, for example, violate human rights or have terrorist or military motives. Such collaborations require the advisory committee to provide recommendations on security measures, etc.

Why is it necessary? The advisory committee on sensitive collaborations with third parties can be facilitated in the RMS-P which allows them to assess the project and provide appropriate recommendations to the researchers and research directors.

Parties involved: Advisory committee, researchers, research directors, and local/ central RMS-P content editors and administrators.

c. Data Management Plan

The Data Management Plans (DMP) can be facilitated in the RMS-P. In the DMP, questions are asked about what data are processed and where they are stored, etc. Additionally, information and advice regarding data management is provided through the DMP in RMS-P.

Why is it necessary? The DMP is necessary for data stewards to check compliance with RDM guidelines for every project. The content of DMPs varies across faculties to align with the specific nature of research and institutional guidelines on RDM.

Parties involved: Researchers, data stewards, and local/ central RMS-P content editors and administrators.

d. Information Security & Privacy Risk Analysis

Incorporating an Information Security and Privacy Risk Analysis (IB&P Risk Analysis) in the RMS-P makes it possible to assess information security and privacy concerns. This assessment contributes to the protection of (sensitive) research data, because it identifies which security measures should be taken regarding the scope and risk profile of the research project. For research projects, the IB&P risk analyses is met through other administrative forms in the RMS-P, such as the DMP. In some cases, for example when implementing new information systems, a more extensive IB&P may be needed and will be initiated by the information security officers.

Why is it necessary? The IB&P Risk Analysis ensures the safeguarding of integrity and confidentiality of research data and protects the institution against security risks.

Parties involved: Researchers, data stewards, security officers, privacy officers, and local/ central RMS-P content editors and administrators.

e. Data Protection Impact Assessment

When the processing of personal data - given its nature and purpose - is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of research participants, an additional assessment to the IB&P Risk Analysis needs to be conducted, the so-called Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA). This assessment guides to systematically analyse, identify and minimise the data protection risks of a research project. The RMS-P can provide all DPIA related workflows, such as the pre-DPIA assessment, and if needed the organisation of a DPIA workshop. A full DPIA workshop can be initiated by data stewards in collaboration with privacy officers, when specific triggers are identified in the RMS-P, such as those arising from the DMP and Ethics Review.

Why is it necessary? The DPIA is required for research in which highly sensitive personal data are processed to minimise data protection risks.

Parties involved: Researchers, data stewards, DPO, CISO, privacy officers, security officers, and local/ central RMS-P content editors and administrators.

B4. Create & Conclude Agreements / Update & Add Agreements

a. Privacy Agreement

The GDPR requires privacy agreements (e.g., data processing agreement, joint controller agreement, standard contractual clauses, etc.), whenever personal data are exchanged between different parties (e.g., universities or companies). The RMS-P can facilitate the drafting of privacy agreements for research projects.

Why is it necessary? A procedure for privacy agreements is necessary for data stewards, sometimes in consultation with the privacy officer or legal department, to check whether a privacy agreement is needed and to be able to create and complete agreements.

Parties involved: Researchers, data stewards, privacy officers, lawyers, research directors, and local/ central RMS-P editors/ administrators.

b. IXA - Collaboration Agreements, NDAs, etc.

Support from IXA, including the expertise of grant advisers, business developers, and legal experts, can be accessed through the RMS-P. IXA supports in valorisation and impact strategies, as well as setting up collaborations with third parties (collaboration agreements) and/or the initiation of new businesses, managing intellectual property and other legal and financial support.

Why is it necessary? IXA lawyers will benefit greatly from having an overview of pending requests. Moreover, data stewards and other support staff can easily find information on previously drafted agreements. In addition, referral to IXA for legal support becomes more convenient when it is incorporated in the RMS-P.

Parties involved: IXA lawyers, researchers, data stewards, privacy officers and local/ central RMS-P editors/ administrators.

c. Data Transfer Agreements

The Data Transfer Agreements (DTA) can be made available to all researchers who want to take data to another institute, for instance when leaving the UvA. Templates are available for DTAs with and without personal data. The data steward plays a role in reviewing and getting the DTA signed, as well as archiving and providing the data.

Why is it necessary? The UvA is responsible for the data and needs to officially transfer this responsibility to the researcher or the researcher's new employer. A workflow is needed in the RMS-P to create, track the progress of, and complete (including signing) a DTA.

Parties involved: Researchers, data stewards, legal support, local/ central RMS-P editors/ administrators.

B5. Organise Studies-Experiments & Request Research (Lab) Facilities

a. Documenting and Planning Studies / Requesting Facilities

The RMS-P can enable researchers to document and plan studies/ experiments, by assisting them with participant recruitment, project advertisement, etc., and by enabling them to request/ book research (lab) facilities, such as rooms, existing/ new instruments and lab support.

Why is it necessary? The UvA offers services enabling researchers to access (lab) facilities and support for their studies/ experiments. The RMS-P aims to serve as a comprehensive portal where researchers can access all necessary information and support for their work, including support for studies/ experiments including the use of research (lab) facilities.

Parties involved: Researchers, lab support, local/ central RMS-P editors/ administrators.

C. IT and (Meta) Data Management

C1. Advice on IT for Project / Request, Manage, & Access IT Facilities

a. Decision Guide for IT Facilities for Data Storage, Management and Analysis

A guide can be included to assess and advise which IT facilities are most suitable for the research project regarding data storage, management, processing, and analysis. Initially, advice will be primarily based on the Data Management Plan (DMP; see B3). In the long run the idea is to create a guidance framework (powered by AI) to optimise not only IT utilisation but also the entire research process from start to finish. By using the guide, researchers receive advice on IT facilities suitable for their research project. Moreover, after the advice researchers should be able to directly request the advised IT facilities and initiate the on-boarding process. When the solution is not straightforward, researchers can receive consultancy on the different available facilities to make a well-informed decision about which ones to pick.

Why is it necessary? This guide can become part of the RMS-P to support researchers in selecting the optimal IT solutions for their projects. This could save researchers time in discovering and obtaining the facilities and RDM/IT support in exploring the best options to advise.

Parties involved: Researchers, data stewards, central IT & RDM support, and local/ central RMS-P content editors/ administrators.

b. User Group and Access Management for IT Facilities

RMS-P can provide support for controlling user groups and access to storage and computing facilities on the basis of roles (e.g. researchers, data stewards, collaborators, students) within the group. More

specifically, coordinating researchers can invite others to join a group for collaboration and can set permissions for group members, ensuring only authorised group members can view, manage, or process research data.

Why is it necessary? Group and access management is essential for collaborations and to maintain data integrity and confidentiality by regulating and tracking access to (sensitive) research data.

Parties involved: Researchers, data stewards/ managers, students, and local/ central IT & RDM support.

C3. Store, Update, Check, & Publish Metadata

a. Metadata Management

Metadata management is a critical aspect of research data management, and it can be supported and facilitated by the RMS-P. Researchers enter project information early in the research lifecycle through various registrations such as DMPs, lab/research journals, and ethics checklists. To enhance efficiency, elements of this project information should be automatically transferred to a central metadata repository, where researchers can further refine, expand, and update the metadata as needed. Moreover, to ensure quality and consistency, data stewards and library staff should be able to review and verify the metadata before it is published to common repositories like Zenodo, OSF, UvA/ HvA Figshare, or DANS. Essentially, the RMS-P can streamline the process of metadata management by providing easy access to the metadata repository and automating the workflow for metadata publication to achieve research exposure.

Why is it necessary? Metadata management contributes to the 'FAIRification' of research data and 'Open Science'. It guarantees that archived research data meet FAIR principles within the institute. Moreover, by publishing metadata, the data become FAIR not just within the institute but also to the wider global research community.

Parties involved: Researchers, data stewards, library, local/ central RMS-P content editors/ administrators.

C4. Check, Archive & Publish Data / Register & Publish Research Output

a. Data Archiving

Data archiving can be facilitated in the RMS-P and should be automated as much as possible. Moreover, a variety of data archiving workflows could be supported, such as moving data from a workspace (e.g., laptop, storage facility, analysis environment) to a closed archive and supporting data quality controls (e.g., is data provenance complete, are metadata correct?).

Why is it necessary? Data archiving support is necessary for researchers and data stewards to archive research data in accordance with laws/ regulations (such as the GDPR) and (institutional) policies. Furthermore, archiving of data in a structured and durable way contributes to research integrity, transparency, reusability, the prevention of data loss, and more.

Parties involved: Researchers, data stewards, local/ central IT & RDM support, local/ central RMS-P content editors/ administrators.

b. Data Publication

Data publication can be facilitated in the RMS-P and should be automated as much as possible. Moreover, data access management can be supported through the RMS-P, with the help of Research Data Exchange (RDX) functionality. RDX manages access on the terms of use (licenses) that can be

specified by the research institute. When the terms of use have been signed, access to data is either available for download or facilitated through a Virtual Research Environment (VRE: online secure research environment supervised by the UvA) in which direct download of the data is not allowed. Notably, this publication route can also accommodate other research outputs, such as research protocols.

Why is it necessary? Data publication support is necessary for researchers to publish their research data according to laws/ regulations, common practice, and (institutional) policies. Early data sharing is in line with the principles of 'Open Science', which aims to promote the progress of science by enabling (interdisciplinary) collaboration, reuse, aggregation, meta-analyses, and to avoid unnecessary duplication of research. By making their data available, researchers also gain more recognition for their work (e.g., additional citations, collaborations, etc.).

Parties involved: Researchers, data stewards, local/ central IT & RDM support, local/ central RMS-P editors/ administrators.

C5. Request Archived Data for Reuse.

a. Data Reuse

Reuse of data from the UvA archive can be facilitated in the RMS-P and should be automated as much as possible. For instance, a workflow can be supported to copy/ download data from the archive to a workspace (e.g., laptop, storage facility, analysis environment). Requests for reuse of data could also be supported by RDX (see C3.) which then manages access to the requested data for non-UvA researchers as well as for UvA researchers.

Why is it necessary? In light of the 'FAIR principles' and 'Open Science', it is important to optimise the reuse of research data by streamlining and automating related workflows.

Parties involved: Researchers, data stewards, local/ central IT & RDM support, local/ central RMS-P content editors/ administrators.

D. Workflow Support

D1. Workflows for Routing, Guidance, & Communication

a. Modular

The RMS-P should be modular and adaptable to fit with the research and support processes of the different faculties and research institutes. This will make it also possible to use particular modules only. In addition, reuse of already registered information is important to avoid duplication of effort. Although RMS-P should be standardised and centralised as much as possible, certain adaptability is required per research institute, providing freedom in functionality and workflow configuration, information provision, etc.

Why is it necessary? A modular and adaptable design for the RMS-P is needed to meet the diversity of the different research institutes with their specific research and support processes. This is also of importance with regard to adoption across the UvA.

Parties involved: Local/ central RMS-P content editors/ administrators.

b. Referral and Guidance

RMS-P requires an advanced and efficient referral system tailored to various functionalities and workflows. For example, the DPIA requires referrals to privacy and security officers, the CISO, the

DPO. Whereas ‘data archiving’ requires referral to a data steward and possibly a data science or statistical expert for quality control. RMS-P should serve as the primary entry point and communication channel for addressing needs, supporting decisions, making referrals, managing documentation, and tracking progress.

Why is it necessary? Researchers should be supported as effectively as possible throughout their projects. Instead of spending time searching for support and information, they should be guided and resourced by the RMS-P to facilitate their research. For example, if a researcher, based on their DMP, decides to use Research Drive for storage and requires IT assistance to set up this storage, the workflow to facilitate this process should be automatically triggered in the RMS-P. This includes making referrals to support staff and streamlining the steps to complete the set-up.

Parties involved: Local/ central RMS-P content editors/ administrators.

3 Concluding remarks

A first draft of this document has been reviewed and discussed with many people from a variety of roles and disciplines (see Appendix A for a list). All are positive about the RMS-P, with strong support for the idea that it should develop into a 'one stop shop', providing easy access to a wide range of information and support, both central and local. There is also a shared desire for its rapid implementation. However, there are clear differences in what respondents prioritise. For example, in faculties that conduct research with human participants, the ethics review module is considered essential, as its absence would jeopardise the progress of their research. In contrast, other faculties place the highest value on easy access to RDM infrastructure and guidance on computing facilities. Notably, this RDM infrastructure is considered overall to be of the utmost importance, but as long as it is under development or lacking, the implementation of its access through the RMS-P will have to wait. The following are some additional remarks and concerns derived from the feedback and discussions in the review process.

- (1) Before selecting or developing a system or tool for the RMS-P, the preferred features for the RMS-P should be analysed more in depth resulting in detailed (non-) functional requirements which form the basis for the selection of a suitable system or provide the directions for new developments.
- (2) Before selecting or developing a system or tool for the RMS-P, it is crucial to engage all relevant stakeholders (see 'parties involved' in the overview of components and modules in chapter 2) and to take technical limitations into account that could hinder ease of use for researchers and support staff.
- (3) When selecting or developing a system or tool for the RMS-P, it is essential to verify that preferred features can be integrated and/or implemented, including commonly requested features such as conditional multi-layered forms, workflow and decision support, and the ability to upload and manage documents for handling support requests and responses.
- (4) Developing and maintaining the RMS-P platform will be managed by the Library and ICTS, but dedicated local RMS-P content editors/ administrators will also be needed. These local representatives are essential to address the unique needs, policies, and guidelines of different research disciplines.
- (5) In developing the RMS-P, the central service support and development team could profit from collaboration with experts within the faculties, such as developers and research support staff of the FMG Research Lab, the FNWI Facultaire Expert-IT OndersteuningsGroep (FEIOG), and the Humanities Labs.
- (6) Developing the RMS-P will be a multi-year project, with ongoing maintenance and structural resources to guarantee sustainability. To support its realisation, a comprehensive business plan and roadmap should be created.
- (7) The RMS-P consists of numerous components and modules that require development and interoperability. However, a phased approach will be sufficient for initial success. Prioritising and identifying the most essential and easily implementable components will be key to achieve early impact and building momentum for the further development of the RMS-P.

- (8) The challenges to scientific integrity are becoming increasingly severe due to factors such as predatory journals, paper mills, and generative AI. The UvA infrastructure, along with early publication of all research output, at every stage, can help mitigate these issues. The RMS-P should prioritise facilitating related processes, including easy archiving with time stamps (C3.a.) and, whenever possible, early publication of research plans (B2.b.), protocols, intermediate products, lab journals (B2.d.), and, of course, research data (C3.b.).
- (9) Connection to underlying infrastructure -such as enabling streamlined data management, automated as much as possible- is widely regarded as a crucial aspect of RMS-P. However, much of this infrastructure is not yet in place. Conducting a fit-gap analysis to identify incomplete and missing infrastructure components is essential, as it will allow for the prioritisation of key development areas and shaping targets on a roadmap.
- (10) The RMS-P will not be presented as a 'one size fits all'. Rather, it must have a modular structure so that research institutes can select the modules relevant to their discipline and exclude those they do not need. A modular structure also allows for discipline-specific modifications when necessary.
- (11) Still, a balance should be struck between implementing custom solutions and maintaining administrative and cost efficiency wherever possible. The implementation of the RMS-P can play an important role in promoting standardisation of procedures and the use of central services.
- (12) The RMS-P is also necessary for promoting compliance with rules and regulations, the code of conduct, open science policies, and secure RDM and research practices. However, compliance should ideally not be enforced through mandatory RMS-P use. Instead, the RMS-P should be designed as the easiest way to conduct research. The RMS-P should be intuitive, and workflows should be structured and automated as much as possible.

Appendix A: Reviewers and Interviewees

This report has been produced with the help of many people working in the faculties and research institutes, in the Library, and at ICTS. We are very grateful to them for their contribution. Below we list the people who reviewed the first draft of the RMS-P product vision.

Faculty / Institute	Reviewers and interviewees ¹
Faculty of Social and Behavioural Sciences (FMG) / Amsterdam Institute for Social Science Research (AISSR)	...
Faculty of Social and Behavioural Sciences (FMG) / Amsterdam School of Communication Research (ASCoR)	...
Faculty of Social and Behavioural Sciences (FMG) / Psychology (PsyRes)	...
Faculty of Social and Behavioural Sciences (FMG) / Research Institute of Child Development and Education (RICDE)	...
Faculty of Social and Behavioural Sciences (FMG) / Project Control	...
FMG research lab	...
Faculty of Humanities (FGw)	...
Faculty of Humanities (FGw) / Project Control	...
Amsterdam Law School (FdR) / Information Law (IvIR)	...
Amsterdam Law School (FdR)	...
Faculty of Economics and Business (FEB) / Amsterdam School of Economics (ASE-RI) & Amsterdam Business School (ABS)	...
Faculty of Science (FNWI) / Computer Science (IvI)	...
Faculty of Science (FNWI) / Biology (IBED)	...
Faculty of Science (FNWI) / Life Sciences (SILS)	...
Faculty of Science (FNWI) / Chemistry (HIMS)	...
Faculty of Science (FNWI) / Anton Pannekoek Institute for Astronomy	...
Faculty of Science (FNWI) / Korteweg-de Vries Instituut	...
Faculty of Science (FNWI) / Informatics Institute	...

¹ The names of the reviewers and interviewees have been omitted in the public version.

Faculty of Science (FNWI) / Institute of Physics	...
Faculty of Science (FNWI)	...
Library's (departments 'Digital Infrastructure' and 'Teaching and Research Support')	...
ICT Services/ Research IT	...
Executive Staff	...
Innovation Exchange Amsterdam (IXA)	...